

Properties of neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals in subtraction semigroups

G. Muhiuddin¹, B. Elavarasan², K. Porselvi³ and D. Al-Kadi⁴

¹ Department of Mathematics, University of Tabuk, P.O. Box-741, Tabuk-71491, Saudi Arabia.

¹ E-mail:chishtygm@gmail.com.

^{2,3}Department of Mathematics, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore - 641 114, India.

²E-mail:belavarasan@gmail.com; ³ E-mail:porselvi94@yahoo.co.in.

⁴ Department of Mathematics and Statistic, College of Science, Taif University, P.O. Box 11099, Taif 21944, Saudi Arabia. ⁴E-mail: d.alkadi@tu.edu.sa

*Correspondence: belavarasan@gmail.com

Abstract. Our aim is to explore the idea of neutrosophic \mathfrak{N} -ideals in near-subtraction semigroups in this article and obtain some outcomes that are equivalent to them. We also illustrate the notion of a neutrosophic \varkappa - intersection. Additionally, in a near-subtraction semigroup, we examine the term homomorphism of a neutrosophic \varkappa - structure and establish some conclusions based on a homomorphic neutrosophic \varkappa - structure preimage of a neutrosophic \varkappa - left (respectively, right) ideal.

Keywords: Semigroups; Subtraction semigroups; neutrosophic \varkappa -structures, neutrosophic \varkappa - ideals, homomorphism.

1. Introduction

In [26], Schein investigated the systems of the type $(\Sigma, \circ, \setminus)$, where Σ is a family of functions closed under the composition \circ of functions (and therefore (Σ, \circ) is a function semigroup) and the set theoretic subtraction \setminus (and therefore (Σ, \setminus) is a subtraction algebra). In [29], Zelinka examined Schein's suggestion for the multiplication structure and discovered a method for resolving a challenge in a kind of subtraction algebra, namely atomic subtraction algebras. In subtraction algebras [11], Jun et al. proposed the idea of ideals by examining the characterisation of ideals. In [10], Jun et al. explored the ideals produced by a set and its associated outcomes. Dheena et al. [1], formed the ideas of near-subtraction semigroups as well as strongly regular near-subtraction semigroups. They found an equivalent assertion for a near-subtraction semigroup to be strongly regular.

Zadeh [30] developed the idea that a fuzzy subset φ of a set K is a map from K into $[0, 1]$. Since then, this concept has been effectively used in a range of applications, including image processing, control systems, engineering, robotics, industrial automation, and optimisation.

In subtraction algebras, Lee et al. [14] established the term fuzzy ideal and made some assertions that a fuzzy set is to be a fuzzy ideal. Prince Williams [28] coined the terms fuzzy ideals and fuzzy intersection in near-subtraction semigroups and homomorphic fuzzy images and preimages of a near-subtraction semigroup.

In [16], Molodtsov introduced a concept, namely the soft set (F, \mathfrak{S}) , which is a mapping from \mathfrak{S} into the power set of \mathbb{U} given a base universe set \mathbb{U} and the gathering of attributes \mathfrak{S} . Jun et al. [12] extended Molodtsov's concept to hybrid structures, a concept that is similar to the theories of soft and fuzzy sets, and proved a number of hybrid structure attributes for a gathering of parameter values over a base universe set. The authors further explored the ideas of hybrid subalgebras, and hybrid fields based on this approach. Several authors produced hybrid concepts in a variety of algebraic structures (See [2–5, 15, 17, 18, 20–23]).

Smarandache came up with neutrophobic sets as a way to deal with the constant unpredictability. It makes intuitionistic fuzzy sets as well as fuzzy sets more broad. Neutrosophic sets can be described by these three things: their membership functions for indeterminacy (I), falsity (F), and truth (T). These sets can be used in a lot of different ways to deal with the problems that come from unclear information. A neutrosophic set can tell the difference between membership functions that are absolute and those that are relative. Smarandache used these collections for non-standard analyses like sports choices (losing, tying, and winning), control theory, decision-making theory, and so on. This area has been studied by several authors(See [8, 9, 27]).

Khan et al. examined ϵ -neutrosophic \varkappa -subsemigroup and a semigroup in [13]. Elavarasan et al. [6] examined the idea of neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals in semigroups. Elavarasan et al. presented neutrosophic filters and bi-filters in a semigroup and examined their properties in [7]. Muhiuddin et al. provided the definitions and characteristics of neutrosophic \varkappa -interior ideals as well as neutrosophic \varkappa - ideals in ordered semigroups in [19].

Porselvi et al. proposed neutrosophic \varkappa -interior ideal structure as well as neutrosophic \varkappa -simple in semigroups in [25], and they obtained comparable statements for the two types of structures. Porselvi et al. [24] described numerous characteristics of a neutrosophic \varkappa -bi-ideal structure in a semigroup and showed that when a semigroup is regular left duo, both a neutrosophic \varkappa -right ideal and a neutrosophic \varkappa -bi-ideal are identical. They discussed analogous claims for the regular semigroup with regard to the neutrosophic \varkappa -product.

This article explores the idea of neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal in near-subtraction semigroups and its associated characteristics. Additionally, we provide examples of a neutrosophic \varkappa -left ideal that is not a neutrosophic \varkappa -right ideal and vice versa. Moreover, we examine and discuss the neutrosophic \varkappa -image, neutrosophic \varkappa -intersection, and neutrosophic \varkappa -preimage of a near-subtraction semigroup using homomorphism.

2. Preliminaries of subtraction semigroups

We compile some basic definitions for near-subtraction semigroups in this portion, which we will use in the next section.

Definition 2.1. [26] A set $\mathfrak{S}(\neq \emptyset)$ with the binary operation “ $-$ ” that fulfils the below assertions is referred to as a subtraction algebra. $\forall q_0, l_0, i_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$,

- (i) $q_0 - (l_0 - q_0) = q_0$.
- (ii) $q_0 - (q_0 - l_0) = l_0 - (l_0 - q_0)$.
- (iii) $(q_0 - l_0) - i_0 = (q_0 - i_0) - l_0$.

The following are some characteristics of a subtraction algebra:

- (i) $q_0 - 0 = q_0$ and $0 - q_0 = 0$.
- (ii) $(q_0 - l_0) - q_0 = 0$.
- (iii) $(q_0 - l_0) - l_0 = q_0 - l_0$.
- (iv) $(q_0 - l_0) - (l_0 - q_0) = q_0 - l_0$, where $0 = q_0 - q_0$ is an element that is independent on the choice of $q_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$.

Definition 2.2. [29] A set $\mathfrak{S}(\neq \emptyset)$ with the binary operations “ $-$ ” and “ \cdot ” that satisfies the following requirements is referred to as a subtraction semigroup:

- (i) $(\mathfrak{S}, -)$ and (\mathfrak{S}, \cdot) are a subtraction algebra and a semigroup, respectively.
- (ii) $l_0(l_1 - l_2) = l_0l_1 - l_0l_2$ and $(l_0 - l_1)l_2 = l_0l_2 - l_1l_2 \forall l_0, l_1, l_2 \in \mathfrak{S}$.

Definition 2.3. [29] A set $\mathfrak{S}(\neq \emptyset)$ with the binary operations “ $-$ ” and “ \cdot ” that satisfy the following requirements is referred to as a near-subtraction semigroup (*NSS* for short):

- (i) $(\mathfrak{S}, -)$ and (\mathfrak{S}, \cdot) are a subtraction algebra and a semigroup, respectively.
- (ii) $(l_0 - l_1)l_2 = l_0l_2 - l_1l_2 \forall l_0, l_1, l_2 \in \mathfrak{S}$.

Clearly $0l_0 = 0 \forall l_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$.

Hereafter, \mathfrak{S} represents the near-subtraction semigroup.

Definition 2.4. If $l_0 - l_1 \in L$ whenever $l_0, l_1 \in L$, then a subset $L(\neq \emptyset)$ of \mathfrak{S} is said to be a subalgebra of \mathfrak{S} .

Definition 2.5. Let $(\mathfrak{S}, -, \cdot)$ be a *NSS*. A subset $\mathfrak{R}(\neq \emptyset)$ of \mathfrak{S} is referred as

- (i) a right ideal whenever \mathfrak{R} is a subalgebra of $(\mathfrak{S}, -)$ and $\mathfrak{R}\mathfrak{S} \subseteq \mathfrak{R}$.
- (ii) a left ideal whenever \mathfrak{R} is a subalgebra of $(\mathfrak{S}, -)$ and $p_1c_1 - p_1(w_1 - c_1) \in \mathfrak{R} \forall p_1, w_1 \in \mathfrak{S}; c_1 \in \mathfrak{R}$.
- (iii) an ideal whenever \mathfrak{R} is both a right and a left ideal.

3. Preliminaries of Neutrosophic \varkappa - structures

This portions outlines the basic ideas of neutrosophic \varkappa -structures of \mathfrak{S} , which are essential for the sequel.

For a set $Q(\neq \emptyset)$, $\mathcal{F}(Q, \mathbb{I}^-)$ is the family of functions with negative-values from a set Q to \mathbb{I}^- , where $\mathbb{I}^- = [-1, 0]$. An element $k_1 \in \mathcal{F}(Q, \mathbb{I}^-)$ is known as a \varkappa -function on Q and \varkappa -structure denotes (Q, k_1) of X .

Definition 3.1. [12] For a set $Q(\neq \emptyset)$, a *neutrosophic \varkappa - structure* of Q is described as below:

$$Q_M := \frac{Q}{(T_M, I_M, F_M)} = \left\{ \frac{v_0}{(T_M(v_0), I_M(v_0), F_M(v_0))} : v_0 \in Q \right\},$$

where T_M on Q means the negative truth membership function, I_M on Q means the negative indeterminacy membership function and F_M on Q means the negative false membership function.

Note 3.2. Q_M satisfies the requirement: $-3 \leq T_M(b_1) + I_M(b_1) + F_M(b_1) \leq 0 \forall b_1 \in Q$.

Definition 3.3. [13] For a set $Q(\neq \emptyset)$, let $Q_J := \frac{Q}{(T_J, I_J, F_J)}$ and $Q_V := \frac{Q}{(T_V, I_V, F_V)}$,

- (i) Q_J is defined as a *neutrosophic \varkappa -substructure* of Q_V , represented by $Q_J \subseteq Q_V$, if it fulfils the below criteria: for any $z_0 \in Q$,

$$T_J(z_0) \geq T_V(z_0), I_J(z_0) \leq I_V(z_0), F_J(z_0) \geq F_V(z_0).$$

If $Q_J \subseteq Q_V$ and $Q_V \subseteq Q_J$, then $Q_J = Q_V$.

- (ii) The intersection of Q_J and Q_V is a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure over Q and is defined as follows: $Q_J \cap Q_V = Q_{J \cap V} = (Q; T_{J \cap V}, I_{J \cap V}, F_{J \cap V})$, where

$$\begin{aligned} (T_J \cap T_V)(h_0) &= T_{J \cap V}(h_0) = T_J(h_0) \vee T_V(h_0), \\ (I_J \cap I_V)(h_0) &= I_{J \cap V}(h_0) = I_J(h_0) \wedge I_V(h_0), \\ (F_J \cap F_V)(h_0) &= F_{J \cap V}(h_0) = F_J(h_0) \vee F_V(h_0) \text{ for any } h_0 \in Q. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. For $V_0 \subseteq Q \neq \emptyset$, consider the neutrosophic \varkappa -structure

$$\chi_{V_0}(Q_D) = \frac{Q}{(\chi_V(T)_D, \chi_V(I)_D, \chi_V(F)_D)},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{V_0}(T)_D : Q &\rightarrow \mathbb{I}^-, j_1 \rightarrow \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } j_1 \in V_0 \\ 0 & \text{if } j_1 \notin V_0, \end{cases} \\ \chi_{V_0}(I)_D : Q &\rightarrow \mathbb{I}^-, j_1 \rightarrow \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j_1 \in V_0 \\ -1 & \text{if } j_1 \notin V_0, \end{cases} \\ \chi_{V_0}(F)_D : Q &\rightarrow \mathbb{I}^-, j_1 \rightarrow \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } j_1 \in V_0 \\ 0 & \text{if } j_1 \notin V_0, \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

which is described as the *characteristic neutrosophic \varkappa -structure* of V_0 over Q .

Definition 3.5. [12] For a nonempty set Q , let $Q_N = \frac{Q}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)}$ and $\bar{\delta}, \varphi, \Theta \in \mathbb{I}^-$ with $-3 \leq \bar{\delta} + \varphi + \Theta \leq 0$. Consider the following sets:

$$T_N^{\bar{\delta}} = \{c_1 \in Q \mid T_N(c_1) \leq \bar{\delta}\}, I_N^{\varphi} = \{c_1 \in Q \mid I_N(c_1) \geq \varphi\}, F_N^{\Theta} = \{c_1 \in Q \mid F_N(c_1) \leq \Theta\}.$$

Then the set $Q_N(\bar{\delta}, \varphi, \Theta) = \{c_1 \in Q \mid T_N(c_1) \leq \bar{\delta}, I_N(c_1) \geq \varphi, F_N(c_1) \leq \Theta\}$ is referred as a $(\bar{\delta}, \varphi, \Theta)$ -level set of Q_N . Note that $Q_N(\bar{\delta}, \varphi, \Theta) = T_N^{\bar{\delta}} \cap I_N^{\varphi} \cap F_N^{\Theta}$.

4. Neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals in subtraction semigroups

The idea of neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals in near-subtraction is defined in this portion. We also develop a case where a neutrosophic \varkappa -right ideal is not a neutrosophic \varkappa -left ideal, and vice versa, and we describe certain properties of a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure's homomorphism in a near-subtraction semigroup.

Definition 4.1. A neutrosophic \varkappa -structure $\mathfrak{S}_B = \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_B, I_B, F_B)}$ of \mathfrak{S} is defined as a *neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal* of \mathfrak{S} if it meets the below axioms:

- (i) $(\forall g_0, l_0 \in \mathfrak{S}) \left(\begin{array}{l} T_B(g_0 - l_0) \leq T_B(g_0) \vee T_B(l_0) \\ I_B(g_0 - l_0) \geq I_B(g_0) \wedge I_B(l_0) \\ F_B(g_0 - l_0) \leq F_B(g_0) \vee F_B(l_0) \end{array} \right).$
- (ii) $(\forall s_0, j_0, l_0 \in \mathfrak{S}) \left(\begin{array}{l} T_B(s_0 l_0 - s_0(j_0 - l_0)) \leq T_B(l_0) \\ I_B(s_0 l_0 - s_0(j_0 - l_0)) \geq I_B(l_0) \\ F_B(s_0 l_0 - s_0(j_0 - l_0)) \leq F_B(l_0) \end{array} \right).$
- (iii) $(\forall l_0, q_0 \in \mathfrak{S}) \left(\begin{array}{l} T_B(l_0 q_0) \leq T_B(l_0) \\ I_B(l_0 q_0) \geq I_B(l_0) \\ F_B(l_0 q_0) \leq F_B(l_0) \end{array} \right).$

Note that \mathfrak{S}_B of \mathfrak{S} is a *neutrosophic \varkappa -left ideal* when (i) and (ii) are hold, and \mathfrak{S}_B of \mathfrak{S} is a *neutrosophic \varkappa -right ideal* when (i) and (iii) are hold.

Notation 1. Let \mathfrak{S} be a NSS. Then we use the below notations:

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_5(\mathfrak{S})$ is the gathering of all neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals of \mathfrak{S} .
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_R(\mathfrak{S})$ is the gathering of all neutrosophic \varkappa -right ideals of \mathfrak{S} .
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_L(\mathfrak{S})$ is the gathering of all neutrosophic \varkappa -left ideals of \mathfrak{S} .

Here are a few examples of neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals.

Example 4.2. Let $\mathfrak{S} = \{0, i_0, p_0\}$ be a set with two operations “ $-$ ” and “ \cdot ” that are represented by the below tables:

-	0	i_0	p_0
0	0	0	0
i_0	i_0	0	i_0
p_0	p_0	p_0	0

.	0	i_0	p_0
0	0	0	0
i_0	0	i_0	0
p_0	i_0	0	p_0

Then $(\mathfrak{S}, -, \cdot)$ is a NSS. Define a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure $\mathfrak{S}_N := \left\{ \frac{0}{(w, l, w_1)}, \frac{i_0}{(r, k, r_1)}, \frac{p_0}{(y, v, y_1)} \right\}$ of \mathfrak{S} for $v, k, l, w, w_1, r, r_1, y, y_1 \in [-1, 0]$.

(i) If $y > r = w; v < k = l$ and $y_1 > r_1 = w_1$, then $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_3(\mathfrak{S})$.

(ii) If $y = r > w; k = v < l$ and $y_1 = r_1 > w_1$, then $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S})$, but $\mathfrak{S}_N \notin \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})$ as $T_N(p_0.0 - p_0(p_0 - 0)) = T_N(i_0) = r \not\leq w = T_N(0); I_N(p_0.0 - p_0(p_0 - 0)) = I_N(i_0) = k \not\leq l = I_N(0)$ and $F_N(p_0.0 - p_0(p_0 - 0)) = F_N(i_0) = r_1 \not\leq w_1 = F_N(0)$.

(iii) If $r > y > w; k < v < l$ and $r_1 > y_1 > w_1$, then \mathfrak{S}_N is neither in $\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S})$ nor in $\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})$ as $T_N(p_0.0 - p_0(i_0 - 0)) = T_N(i_0) = r \not\leq w = T_N(0), I_N(p_0.0 - p_0(i_0 - 0)) = I_N(i_0) = k \not\leq l = I_N(0), F_N(p_0.0 - p_0(i_0 - 0)) = F_N(i_0) = r_1 \not\leq w_1 = F_N(0)$ and $T_N(p_0.0) = T_N(i_0) = r \not\leq y = T_N(p_0), I_N(p_0.0) = I_N(i_0) = k \not\leq v = I_N(p_0), F_N(p_0.0) = F_N(i_0) = r_1 \not\leq y_1 = F_N(p_0)$. But it fulfils the assertion (i) of Definition 4.1.

Example 4.3. Let $\mathfrak{S} = \{0, r, l, k\}$ be a set with two operations “-” and “.” are given by

-	0	r	l	k
0	0	0	0	0
r	r	0	k	l
l	l	0	0	l
k	k	0	k	0

.	0	r	l	k
0	0	0	0	0
r	0	r	l	k
l	0	0	0	0
k	0	r	l	k

Then $(\mathfrak{S}, -, \cdot)$ is a NSS. For $p, w, n, m, m_1, y, y_1, s, s_1 \in [-1, 0]$, define a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure $\mathfrak{S}_N := \left\{ \frac{0}{(m,p,m_1)}, \frac{r}{(y,w,y_1)}, \frac{l}{(s,n,s_1)}, \frac{k}{(s,n,s_1)} \right\}$ of \mathfrak{S} . If $s > y > m, n < w < p$ and $s_1 > y_1 > m_1$, then $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})$, but $\mathfrak{S}_N \notin \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S})$ as $T_N(r.l) = T_N(l) = s \not\leq y = T_N(r), I_N(r.l) = I_N(l) = n \not\leq w = I_N(r)$ and $F_N(r.l) = F_N(l) = s_1 \not\leq y_1 = F_N(r)$.

Theorem 4.4. For $\mathfrak{S}_N = \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)}$, the listed assertions are equivalent:

- (i) For any $\varrho, \lambda, \nu \in \mathbb{I}^-$, $\mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu) (\neq \phi)$ of \mathfrak{S} is a left(right) ideal,
- (ii) $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})$ ($\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S})$).

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $c, z \in \mathfrak{S}$. Then $T_N(c) = q_1; F_N(c) = r_1; I_N(c) = t_1$ and $T_N(z) = q_2; F_N(z) = r_2; I_N(z) = t_2$, for some $q_1, q_2, t_1, t_2, r_1, r_2 \in \mathbb{I}^-$.

If $q = \max\{q_1, q_2\}; t = \min\{t_1, t_2\}$ and $r = \max\{r_1, r_2\}$, then $T_N(c) \leq q; I_N(c) \geq t; F_N(c) \leq r$ and $T_N(z) \leq q; I_N(z) \geq t; F_N(z) \leq r$, so $c, z \in \mathfrak{S}_N(q, t, r)$. By assumption, we get $c - z \in \mathfrak{S}_N(q, t, r)$ which implies $T_N(c - z) \leq q = T_N(c) \vee T_N(z); I_N(c - z) \geq t = I_N(c) \wedge I_N(z); F_N(c - z) \leq r = F_N(c) \vee F_N(z)$.

For any $n_0, v \in \mathfrak{S}$, we have $n_0c - n_0(v - c) \in \mathfrak{S}_N(q_1, t_1, r_1)$ which implies $T_N(n_0c - n_0(v - c)) \leq q_1 = T_N(c), I_N(n_0c - n_0(v - c)) \geq t_1 = I_N(c), F_N(n_0c - n_0(v - c)) \leq r_1 = F_N(c)$. So $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})$.

Also, for $r \in \mathfrak{S}$, we have $cr \in \mathfrak{S}_N(q_1, t_1, r_1)$ which implies $T_N(cr) \leq q_1 = T_N(c); I_N(cr) \geq t_1 = I_N(c); F_N(cr) \leq r_1 = F_N(c)$. So $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $q, z \in \mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$. Then $T_N(q - z) \leq T_N(q) \vee T_N(z) \leq \varrho; I_N(q - z) \geq I_N(q) \wedge I_N(z) \geq \lambda$ and $F_N(q - z) \leq F_N(q) \vee F_N(z) \leq \nu$ which imply $q - z \in \mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$.

Also, $T_N(qz) \leq T_N(q) \leq \varrho; I_N(qz) \geq I_N(q) \geq \lambda$ and $F_N(qz) \leq F_N(q) \leq \nu$ imply that $qz \in \mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$. So $\mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$ of \mathfrak{S} is a right ideal.

For $l \in \mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$ and $s, j \in \mathfrak{S}$, we have $T_N(sl - s(j - l)) \leq T_N(l) = \varrho; I_N(sl - s(j - l)) \geq I_N(l) = \lambda$ and $F_N(sl - s(j - l)) \leq F_N(l) = \nu$ which imply $sl - s(j - l) \in \mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$.

So, $\mathfrak{S}_N(\varrho, \lambda, \nu)$ of \mathfrak{S} is a left ideal.

We have the succeeding corollary as a outcome of the Theorem 4.4.

Corollary 4.5. For $\emptyset \neq D \subseteq \mathfrak{S}$, a neutrosophic \varkappa - structure $\mathfrak{S}_N = \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)}$ of \mathfrak{S} is characterized as below: For $g_1, l_1, \omega_1, t_1, s_1, v_1 \in [-1, 0]$,

$$T_N(y_0) := \begin{cases} g_1 & \text{if } y_0 \in D \\ l_1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}; \quad I_N(y_0) := \begin{cases} \omega_1 & \text{if } y_0 \in D \\ t_1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}; \quad F_N(y_0) := \begin{cases} s_1 & \text{if } y_0 \in D \\ v_1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $g_1 < l_1; \omega_1 > t_1$ and $s_1 < v_1$ in $[-1, 0]$, the mentioned below statements are equivalent:

- (i) $\mathfrak{S}_N \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})(\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S}))$,
- (ii) D of \mathfrak{S} is a left(right) ideal.

Corollary 4.6. For $\emptyset \neq L \subseteq \mathfrak{S}$ and $\mathfrak{S}_N = \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)}$, the listed below statements are equivalent:

- (i) $\chi_L(\mathfrak{S}_N) \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})(\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S}))$,
- (ii) L of \mathfrak{S} is a left(right) ideal.

Theorem 4.7. Let $\mathfrak{S}_N = \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_N, I_N, F_N)} \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})(\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S}))$. Then the sets $T_N^0 = \{c_1 \in Q \mid T_N(c_1) = T_N(0)\}, I_N^0 = \{c_1 \in Q \mid I_N(c_1) = I_N(0)\}, F_N^0 = \{c_1 \in Q \mid F_N(c_1) = F_N(0)\}$ of \mathfrak{S} are left (right) ideals.

Proof: For $l_0, w_0 \in T_N^0 \cap I_N^0 \cap F_N^0$, we have $T_N(l_0 - w_0) \leq T_N(l_0) \vee T_N(w_0) = T_N(0)$, $I_N(l_0 - w_0) \geq I_N(l_0) \wedge I_N(w_0) = I_N(0)$ and $F_N(l_0 - w_0) \leq F_N(l_0) \vee F_N(w_0) = F_N(0)$. So $l_0 - w_0 \in T_N^0 \cap I_N^0 \cap F_N^0$.

For $s \in \mathfrak{S}$, we have $T_N(sl_0 - s(w_0 - l_0)) \leq T_N(l_0) = T_N(0)$, $I_N(sl_0 - s(w_0 - l_0)) \geq I_N(l_0) = I_N(0)$ and $F_N(sl_0 - s(w_0 - l_0)) \leq F_N(l_0) = F_N(0)$. So $sl_0 - s(w_0 - l_0) \in T_N^0 \cap I_N^0 \cap F_N^0$.

Therefore T_N^0, I_N^0 and F_N^0 are left ideals.

Theorem 4.8. Let $\mathfrak{S}_J := \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_J, I_J, F_J)}$ and $\mathfrak{S}_W := \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_W, I_W, F_W)}$ be the neutrosophic \varkappa -structures in \mathfrak{S} . If $\mathfrak{S}_J, \mathfrak{S}_W \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})(\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S}))$, then $\mathfrak{S}_J \cap \mathfrak{S}_W \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{L}}(\mathfrak{S})(\mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{S}))$.

Proof: Let $w_1, f_1 \in \mathfrak{S}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} T_{J \cap W}(f_1 - w_1) &= (T_J \cap T_W)(f_1 - w_1) \\ &= T_J(f_1 - w_1) \vee T_W(f_1 - w_1) \\ &\leq \{T_J(f_1) \vee T_J(w_1)\} \vee \{T_W(f_1) \vee T_W(w_1)\} \\ &= (T_J \cap T_W)(f_1) \vee (T_J \cap T_W)(w_1) = T_{J \cap W}(f_1) \vee T_{J \cap W}(w_1), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{J \cap W}(f_1 - w_1) &= (I_J \cap I_W)(f_1 - w_1) \\
 &= I_J(f_1 - w_1) \wedge I_W(f_1 - w_1) \\
 &\geq \{I_J(f_1) \wedge I_J(w_1)\} \wedge \{I_W(f_1) \wedge I_W(w_1)\} \\
 &= (I_J \cap I_W)(f_1) \wedge (I_J \cap I_W)(w_1) = I_{J \cap W}(f_1) \wedge I_{J \cap W}(w_1), \\
 F_{J \cap W}(f_1 - w_1) &= (F_J \cap F_W)(f_1 - w_1) \\
 &= F_J(f_1 - w_1) \vee F_W(f_1 - w_1) \\
 &\leq \{F_J(f_1) \vee F_J(w_1)\} \vee \{F_W(f_1) \vee F_W(w_1)\} \\
 &= (F_J \cap F_W)(f_1) \vee (F_J \cap F_W)(w_1) = F_{J \cap W}(f_1) \vee F_{J \cap W}(w_1).
 \end{aligned}$$

For $s_1 \in \mathfrak{S}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{J \cap W}(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) &= (T_J \cap T_W)(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &= T_J(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \vee T_W(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &\leq T_J(w_1) \vee T_W(w_1) = (T_J \cap T_W)(w_1), \\
 I_{J \cap W}(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) &= (I_J \cap I_W)(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &= I_J(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \wedge I_W(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &\geq I_J(w_1) \wedge I_W(w_1) = (I_J \cap I_W)(w_1), \\
 F_{J \cap W}(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) &= (F_J \cap F_W)(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &= F_J(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \vee F_W(s_1 w_1 - s_1(f_1 - w_1)) \\
 &\leq F_J(w_1) \vee F_W(w_1) = (F_J \cap F_W)(w_1).
 \end{aligned}$$

So, $\mathfrak{S}_J \cap \mathfrak{S}_W \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathfrak{S})$.

Hereafter, the symbols \mathfrak{S} and \mathfrak{S}' denote the near-subtraction semigroups.

Definition 4.9. A homomorphism ξ of \mathfrak{S} into \mathfrak{S}' such that $\xi(w_1 - a_1) = \xi(w_1) - \xi(a_1)$ and $\xi(w_1 a_1) = \xi(w_1)\xi(a_1) \forall w_1, a_1 \in \mathfrak{S}$ is defined.

Definition 4.10. Consider a mapping $\Omega : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}$, where $\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{M} \neq \{\phi\}$. Suppose $\mathbb{M}_S := \frac{\mathbb{M}}{(T_S, I_S, F_S)}$ over \mathbb{M} is a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure. Then, under Ω , the preimage of \mathbb{M}_S is described as a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure $\Omega^{-1}(\mathbb{M}_S) = \frac{\mathbb{N}}{(\Omega^{-1}(T_S), \Omega^{-1}(I_S), \Omega^{-1}(F_S))}$ over \mathbb{N} , where $\Omega^{-1}(T_S)(l_0) = T_S(\Omega(l_0))$, $\Omega^{-1}(I_S)(l_0) = I_S(\Omega(l_0))$ and $\Omega^{-1}(F_S)(l_0) = F_S(\Omega(l_0))$ for all $l_0 \in \mathbb{N}$.

Theorem 4.11. Let $\Omega : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}'$ be a homomorphism of NSS. If $\mathfrak{S}'_S \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{S}'}(\mathfrak{S}')$, where $\mathfrak{S}'_S := \frac{\mathfrak{S}'}{(T_S, I_S, F_S)}$, then $\Omega^{-1}(\mathfrak{S}'_S) \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathfrak{S})$.

Proof: Let $k_0, g_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(k_0 - g_0) &= T_S(\Omega(k_0 - g_0)) = T_S(\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(g_0)) \\
 &\leq T_S(\Omega(k_0)) \vee T_S(\Omega(g_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(k_0) \vee \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(g_0),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(k_0 - g_0) &= I_S(\Omega(k_0 - g_0)) = I_S(\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(g_0)) \\ &\geq I_S(\Omega(k_0)) \wedge I_S(\Omega(g_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(k_0) \wedge \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(g_0), \\ \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(k_0 - g_0) &= F_S(\Omega(k_0 - g_0)) = F_S(\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(g_0)) \\ &\leq F_S(\Omega(k_0)) \vee F_S(\Omega(g_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(k_0) \vee \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(g_0). \end{aligned}$$

Let $q_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0)) &= T_S(\Omega(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= T_S(\Omega(q_0k_0) - \Omega(q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= T_S(\Omega(q_0)\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(q_0)(\Omega(g_0) - \Omega(k_0))) \\ &\leq T_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(k_0), \\ \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0)) &= I_S(\Omega(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= I_S(\Omega(q_0k_0) - \Omega(q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= I_S(\Omega(q_0)\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(q_0)(\Omega(g_0) - \Omega(k_0))) \\ &\geq I_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(k_0), \\ \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0)) &= F_S(\Omega(q_0k_0 - q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= F_S(\Omega(q_0k_0) - \Omega(q_0(g_0 - k_0))) \\ &= F_S(\Omega(q_0)\Omega(k_0) - \Omega(q_0)(\Omega(g_0) - \Omega(k_0))) \\ &\leq F_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(k_0). \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(k_0g_0) &= T_S(\Omega(k_0g_0)) = T_S(\Omega(k_0)\Omega(g_0)) \leq T_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(T_S)(k_0), \\ \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(k_0g_0) &= I_S(\Omega(k_0g_0)) = I_S(\Omega(k_0)\Omega(g_0)) \geq I_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(I_S)(k_0), \\ \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(k_0g_0) &= F_S(\Omega(k_0g_0)) = F_S(\Omega(k_0)\Omega(g_0)) \leq F_S(\Omega(k_0)) = \Omega^{-1}(F_S)(k_0). \end{aligned}$$

So, $\Omega^{-1}(\mathfrak{S}'_S) \in \mathcal{N}'_3(\mathfrak{S})$.

Definition 4.12. Consider a onto map $\Omega : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}$, where $\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{M} \neq \{\phi\}$. Suppose $\mathbb{N}_{\mathcal{B}} := \frac{\mathbb{N}}{(T_{\mathcal{B}}, I_{\mathcal{B}}, F_{\mathcal{B}})}$ over \mathbb{N} is a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure. Then, under Ω , the image of $\mathbb{N}_{\mathcal{B}}$ is described as a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure

$$\Omega(\mathbb{N}_{\mathcal{B}}) = \frac{\mathbb{M}}{(\Omega(T_{\mathcal{B}}), \Omega(I_{\mathcal{B}}), \Omega(F_{\mathcal{B}}))}$$

over \mathbb{M} , where, for all $y_2 \in \mathbb{M}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(T_{\mathcal{B}})(y_2) &= \bigwedge_{y_1 \in \Omega^{-1}(y_2)} T_{\mathcal{B}}(y_1), \\ \Omega(I_{\mathcal{B}})(y_2) &= \bigvee_{y_1 \in \Omega^{-1}(y_2)} I_{\mathcal{B}}(y_1), \\ \Omega(F_{\mathcal{B}})(y_2) &= \bigwedge_{y_1 \in \Omega^{-1}(y_2)} F_{\mathcal{B}}(y_1). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.13. Let $\xi : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}'$ be an onto homomorphism of NSS and $\mathfrak{S}'_{\mathcal{X}} := \frac{\mathfrak{S}'}{(T_{\mathcal{X}}, I_{\mathcal{X}}, F_{\mathcal{X}})}$ is a neutrosophic \varkappa -structure of \mathfrak{S}' . If $\xi^{-1}(\mathfrak{S}'_{\mathcal{X}}) \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathfrak{S})$, then $\mathfrak{S}'_{\mathcal{X}} \in \mathcal{N}_{\mathfrak{S}'}(\mathfrak{S}')$.

Proof: Let $v'_0, r'_0 \in \mathfrak{S}'$. Then $\exists v_0, r_0 \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that $\xi(v_0) = v'_0$ and $\xi(r_0) = r'_0$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0 - r'_0) &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0) - \xi(r_0)) = T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0 - r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0 - r_0) \\ &\leq \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) \vee \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{X}})(r_0) \\ &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) \vee T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(r_0)) \\ &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0) \vee T_{\mathcal{X}}(r'_0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0 - r'_0) &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0) - \xi(r_0)) = I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0 - r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0 - r_0) \\ &\geq \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) \wedge \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{X}})(r_0) \\ &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) \wedge I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(r_0)) \\ &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0) \wedge I_{\mathcal{X}}(r'_0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0 - r'_0) &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0) - \xi(r_0)) = F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0 - r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0 - r_0) \\ &\leq \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) \vee \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{X}})(r_0) \\ &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) \vee F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(r_0)) \\ &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0) \vee F_{\mathcal{X}}(r'_0). \end{aligned}$$

Let $s'_0 \in \mathfrak{S}'$. Then $\exists s \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that $\xi(s) = s'_0$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\mathcal{X}}(s'_0 v'_0 - s'_0(r'_0 - v'_0)) &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(s)\xi(v_0) - \xi(s)(\xi(r_0) - \xi(v_0))) \\ &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s)\xi(r_0 - v_0)) \\ &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{X}})(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0)) \leq \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) = T_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) = T_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\mathcal{X}}(s'_0 v'_0 - s'_0(r'_0 - v'_0)) &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(s)\xi(v_0) - \xi(s)(\xi(r_0) - \xi(v_0))) \\ &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s)\xi(r_0 - v_0)) \\ &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{X}})(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0)) \geq \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) = I_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) = I_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\mathcal{X}}(s'_0 v'_0 - s'_0(r'_0 - v'_0)) &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(s)\xi(v_0) - \xi(s)(\xi(r_0) - \xi(v_0))) \\ &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s)\xi(r_0 - v_0)) \\ &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0) - \xi(s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0))) \\ &= \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{X}})(sv_0 - s(r_0 - v_0)) \leq \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{X}})(v_0) = F_{\mathcal{X}}(\xi(v_0)) = F_{\mathcal{X}}(v'_0). \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$T_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0 r'_0) = T_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0 r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0 r_0) \leq \xi^{-1}(T_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0) = T_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0)) = T_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0),$$

$$I_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0 r'_0) = I_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0 r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0 r_0) \geq \xi^{-1}(I_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0) = I_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0)) = I_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0),$$

$$F_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0 r'_0) = F_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0 r_0)) = \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0 r_0) \leq \xi^{-1}(F_{\mathcal{F}})(v_0) = F_{\mathcal{F}}(\xi(v_0)) = F_{\mathcal{F}}(v'_0).$$

So, $\mathfrak{S}'_{\mathcal{F}} \in \mathcal{N}_3(\mathfrak{S}')$.

Definition 4.14. A neutrosophic \varkappa -structure $\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{B}} := \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_{\mathcal{B}}, I_{\mathcal{B}}, F_{\mathcal{B}})}$ is defined to fulfil the sup property in \mathfrak{S} if $\forall S \subseteq \mathfrak{S}, \exists l_0 \in S : T_{\mathcal{B}}(l_0) = \bigwedge_{l \in S} T_{\mathcal{B}}(l); I_{\mathcal{B}}(l_0) = \bigvee_{l \in S} I_{\mathcal{B}}(l); F_{\mathcal{B}}(l_0) = \bigwedge_{l \in S} F_{\mathcal{B}}(l)$.

Proposition 4.15. A homomorphic image of a neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal having sup property is a neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal.

Proof: Let $\varrho : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}'$ be a homomorphism of *NSS* and let $\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{F}} := \frac{\mathfrak{S}}{(T_{\mathcal{F}}, I_{\mathcal{F}}, F_{\mathcal{F}})}$ of \mathfrak{S} be a neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal having sup property.

Suppose $\varrho(b), \varrho(w) \in \mathfrak{S}'$ and let $b_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))$ and $w_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))$ be such that

$$T_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0), \quad I_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0), \quad F_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0),$$

$$T_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0), \quad I_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) = \bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0), \quad F_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w)) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \leq T_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) \vee T_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) \\ &= \left(\bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \vee \left(\bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \\ &= \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)) \vee \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(w)), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w)) &= \bigvee_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \geq I_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) \wedge I_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) \\ &= \left(\bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \\ &= \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)) \wedge \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(w)), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w)) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b) - \varrho(w))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \leq F_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) \vee F_{\mathcal{F}}(w_0) \\ &= \left(\bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \vee \left(\bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(w))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) \right) \\ &= \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)) \vee \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(w)). \end{aligned}$$

Given $\varrho(s) \in \mathfrak{S}'$ and let $s_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(s))$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b))) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b)))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \\ &\leq T_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)), \\ \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b))) &= \bigvee_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b)))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \\ &\geq I_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)), \\ \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b))) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(s)\varrho(b) - \varrho(s)(\varrho(w) - \varrho(b)))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \\ &\leq F_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)). \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)\varrho(w)) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b)\varrho(w))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \leq T_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} T_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(T_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)), \\ \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)\varrho(w)) &= \bigvee_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b)\varrho(w))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \geq I_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigvee_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} I_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(I_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)), \\ \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)\varrho(w)) &= \bigwedge_{z \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b)\varrho(w))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(z) \leq F_{\mathcal{F}}(b_0) = \bigwedge_{k_0 \in \varrho^{-1}(\varrho(b))} F_{\mathcal{F}}(k_0) = \varrho(F_{\mathcal{F}})(\varrho(b)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\varrho(\mathfrak{S}_{\mathcal{F}})$ is a neutrosophic \varkappa -ideal of $\varrho(\mathfrak{S})$.

5. Conclusion

We defined and examined neutrosophic \varkappa - ideals in near-subtraction semigroups in this article. We formed ideals for a neutrosophic \varkappa - ideal in a near-subtraction semigroup, and we also obtained various aspects of the neutrosophic \varkappa - image as well as the neutrosophic \varkappa - preimage of a near-subtraction semigroup using homomorphism mapping. In our future research work, we will explore the notion of a neutrosophic \varkappa - prime ideal and its related properties in near-subtraction semigroups using the ideas and findings presented in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their sincere thanks to the referees for valuable comments and suggestions which improve the paper a lot.

References

1. Dheena, P.; Satheesh kumar, G. On strongly regular near-subtraction semigroups. Commun. Korean Math. Soc. 2007, 22(3), 323–330.
2. Elavarasan, B.; Porselvi, K.; Jun, Y.B. Hybrid generalized bi-ideals in semigroups. International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science 2019, 14(3), 601–612.

3. Elavarasan, B.; Jun, Y.B. Hybrid ideals in semirings. *Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal* 2020, 9(3), 1349–1357.
4. Elavarasan, B.; Muhiuddin, G.; Porselvi, K.; Jun, Y. B. Hybrid structures applied to ideals in near-rings. *Complex & Intell Syst.* 2021, 7(3), 1489–1498.
5. Elavarasan, B.; Jun, Y. B. Regularity of semigroups in terms of hybrid ideals and hybrid bi-ideals. *Kragujev. J. Math.* 2022, 46(6), 857–864.
6. Elavarasan, B.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y. B. Neutrosophic \varkappa -ideals in semigroups. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2019, 28, 274 –280.
7. Elavarasan, B.; Porselvi, K.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y. B.; Muhiuddin, G. Neutrosophic N-filters in semigroups. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2022, 50, 515 –531.
8. Hezam, I. M. An Intelligent Decision Support Model for Optimal Selection of Machine Tool under Uncertainty: Recent Trends. *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications* 2023, 3, 35 – 44.
9. Jdid, M.; Smarandache, F.; Broumi, S. Inspection Assignment Form for Product Quality Control Using Neutrosophic Logic. *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications* 2023 , 1, 4–13.
10. Jun, Y. B.; Kim, H. S. On ideals in subtraction algebras. *Sci. Math. Jpn.* 2007, 65(1), 129–134.
11. Jun, Y. B.; Kim, H. S.; Roh, E. H. Ideal theory of subtraction algebras. *Sci. Math. Jpn.* 2005, 61(3), 459–464.
12. Jun, Y. B.; Song, S. Z.; Muhiuddin, G. Hybrid structures and applications. *Annals of communications in Mathematics.* 2018, 1(1), 11–25.
13. Khan, M.; Anis, S.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y. B. Neutrosophic \varkappa -structures and their applications in semigroups. *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics* 2017, 14(6), 583 – 598.
14. Lee, K. J.; Park, C. H. Some questions on fuzzifications of ideals in subtraction algebras. *Commun. Korean Math. Soc.* 2007, 22(3), 359–363.
15. Meenakshi, S.; Muhiuddin, G.; Elavarasan, B.; Al-Kadi, D. Hybrid ideals in near-subtraction semigroups. *AIMS Mathematics* 2022, 7(7), 13493–13507.
16. Molodtsov, D. Soft set theory-first results. *Comput. Math. Appl.* 1999, 37, 19–31.
17. Muhiuddin, G.; Grace John, J. C.; Elavarasan, B.; Jun, Y. B.; Porselvi, K. Hybrid structures applied to modules over semirings. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 2022, 42(3), 2521–2531.
18. Muhiuddin, G.; Catherine Grace John, J.; Elavarasan, B.; Porselvi, K.; Al-Kadi, D. Properties of k-hybrid ideals in ternary semiring. *J Intell Fuzzy Syst.* 2022 , 42(6), 5799–5807.
19. Muhiuddin, G.; Porselvi, K.; Elavarasan, B.; Al-Kadi, D. Neutrosophic N-Structures in Ordered Semigroups. *Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences* 2022, 130(3).
20. Porselvi, K.; Elavarasan, B. On hybrid interior ideals in semigroups. *Probl. Anal. Issues Anal.* 2019, 8(26)(3), 137 –146.
21. Porselvi, K.; Elavarasan, B.; Jun, Y. B. Hybrid Interior Ideals in Ordered Semigroups. *New Math. Nat. Comput.* 2022, 18(1), 1 –8.
22. Porselvi, K.; Muhiuddin, G.; Elavarasan, B.; Assiry, A. Hybrid Nil Radical of a Ring. *Symmetry* 2022, 14(7), 1367.
23. Porselvi, K.; Muhiuddin, G.; Elavarasan, B.; Jun, Y. B.; Catherine Grace John, J. Hybrid ideals in an AG-groupoid. *New Math. Nat. Comput.* 2023, 19(1), 289 – 305.
24. Porselvi, K.; Elavarasan, B.; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y. B. Neutrosophic \varkappa -bi-ideals in semigroups. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2020, 35, 422–434.
25. Porselvi, K.; Elavarasan, B.; Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic \varkappa -interior ideals in semigroups. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2020, 36, 70 – 80.
26. Schein, B.M. Difference Semigroups. *Commun. Algebra.* 1992, 20(8), 2153–2169.
27. Sleem, A.; Mostafa, N.; Elhenawy, I. Neutrosophic CRITIC MCDM Methodology for Ranking Factors and Needs of Customers in Product’s Target Demographic in Virtual Reality Metaverse. *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications* 2023, 2, 55– 65.
28. Williams, D. R. P. Fuzzy ideals in near-subtraction semigroups. *International scholarly and scientific research and innovation* 2008, 2(7), 625–632.
29. Zelinka, B. Subtraction Semigroups. *Math. Bohem.* 1995 ,120(4), 445–447.
30. Zadeh, L. A. Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control* 1965, 8, 338–353.

Received: July 1, 2023. Accepted: Nov 19, 2023